

Acceptability of Online Examinations and Educational Development in Nigerian Universities: Experience from Distance and E-learning Practice

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Abstract

The adoption of online examinations in tertiary institutions, particularly during and after the COVID-19 era, has gained traction due to its potential to enhance learning outcomes. However, its adaptability and flexibility also make it susceptible to misuse, posing challenges to widespread acceptance and adoption. The extent to which online examinations influence educational development within Nigerian universities, especially in the context of distance and eLearning practices remains underexplored. This study examines stakeholders' perceptions of factors influencing the acceptance and adoption of online examinations and their impact on educational development in Nigerian universities. Using a purposive sampling technique, an online survey was conducted with 216 staff members of Ladoke Akintola University, Distance and eLearning Centre, including LSS, IAG, Technical Support, e-tutors/lecturers, and center administrators. A total of 197 valid responses were obtained, representing a 91% retrieval rate. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and multiple regression at a 95% confidence level. The findings reveal that variables such as Performance Expectancy, Social Influence, and Personal Innovativeness significantly influence online examination adoption and are positively correlated with educational development ($P < 0.0001$). This underscores the importance of these factors in driving the acceptance and effective implementation of online examination practices. By prioritizing these variables, educational institutions can foster greater adoption of online examinations, ultimately enhancing learning outcomes and contributing to the broader goals of educational development. Consequently, it is recommended that Nigerian universities, particularly those embracing distance education, prioritize improving technology infrastructure and investing in capacity building to strengthen online examination systems and practices

Keywords: Online Examination, Nigerian Universities, eLearning, Technology Acceptance, Educational Development

Introduction

Examination plays a crucial role in the learning process, it gives tangible proof of what is learned, gauges student progress, and indicates a grasp of the subject content. For centuries, pen-to-paper has been the most employed mode of assessment delivery to evaluate learners and measure educational achievements in all forms of education, from elementary to tertiary. However, the past three decades have witnessed a sporadic yet progressive transition in the modalities and structures of assessments. The arrival and introduction of computers in the early 90s and their generational evolution over time, introducing new features and capabilities, have led to the development and usage of what is now popularly referred to as “digital assessment”. As technology develops, new and creative digital assessment approaches are being created to evaluate learners utilizing various digital tools at different learning levels (Boitshwarelo *et al.*, 2017). In addition to the technological advancements, studies have linked a rise in student enrolment in educational institutions as another factor contributing to the transition from paper-based assessments to digital ones, as the resources required (time, money, and effort among others) for grading and delivering high-quality feedback rise along with the number of learners in the learning groups or courses (Jonsdottir *et al.*, 2017). Research have shown that digital technologies may assist to revolutionize education, as it tends to be a more student-centred and technology-mediated method of learning (Alessio *et al.*, 2017; Boldyrevskii *et al.*, 2022; Keane *et al.*, 2022; Mari State University *et al.*, 2022). It offers potentially advantageous qualities such as affordances and provides more individualized, flexible, and palatable experiences to the learners (Keane *et al.*, 2022).

Online education activities are increasingly used in educational setting, and it is aimed to develop traditional educational methods (White & Hammer, 2000) and to contribute to solutions of some problems encountered in traditional education such as difficulties experienced due to education in very crowded classrooms or inability to listen to lesson again (Ocak & Karakuş 2021)). Moreover, online education both changed basic structure of information exchange and enabled teachers to make changes in teaching techniques (White & Hammer, 2000). Today qualified online education is much more important that it should be at same level as face-to-face education . Online education has benefits such as flexibility, ease of access to education at appropriate time, and learning anytime, anywhere (Robles & Braathen, 2002; Keskin & Guneş, 2015). However, in addition to these facilities, it has some shortcomings also. In online education, since instructor and students are not physically in same environment and face-to-face communication cannot be achieved, assessment is done differently. This situation requires use of alternative assessment methods and assessment process needs to be more transparent and support learning since assessment helps determining quality of learning (Arend, 2007).

Online examination (OE) is digital assessment format where students can participate in exams remotely, from any location with internet access. To prevent cheating, this mode of exam is usually invigilated either by a human via a webcam, microphone, and other digital tools (Cherry *et al.*, 2021) or through the use of an artificial intelligence (AI) powered agent that monitors examinee activities (Paredes *et al.*, 2021). Digital assessments gained popularity due to their ability to address the aforementioned lockdown constraints as well as the benefits it provides such as remote administration, personalization of learning resources, automation of learning processes, and instant feedback to all stakeholders (Alruwais *et al.*, 2018). As a result, within minimal time, educational institutions began utilizing robust forms of online assessments such as simulation-based assessments and proctored exams to evaluate educational

outcomes and assess students' knowledge and skills. Proctored assessments became a crucial technology for evaluating students during and after the pandemic, resulting in a "new normal" that transformed the educational experience for future generations (Kharbat & Abu-Daibes, 2021).

In recent years, the integration of Online examination has emerged as a crucial component in enhancing the educational experience within Higher Learning Institutions (HLIs) worldwide, aiming to accommodate the learning preferences of digital natives. Despite this trend, as highlighted by Mayhew (2018), the transition to institutional Online examination remains intricate and challenging. Educators in HLIs are confronted with the task of developing and implementing pedagogical strategies that effectively cater to the learning needs of digital natives, as emphasized by Jönsson & Eriksson (2019). According to Ndibalema (2021), the successful implementation of Online examination necessitates not only technological proficiency but also a thoughtful pedagogical shift towards individualized facilitation to align with the learning expectations of 21st-century digital natives.

Existing literature on technology adoption has introduced various models aimed at elucidating the patterns of acceptance and adoption behavior towards emerging technologies. One prominent model is the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) proposed by Venkatesh et al., (2003). According to UTAUT, the determinants of acceptance and adoption of emerging technologies are influenced by variables such as Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, Social Influence, and Facilitating Conditions. However, there remains a gap in the literature concerning the extent to which variables like Performance Expectancy, Social Influence, and Personal Innovativeness contribute as determinants of acceptance and adoption specifically in the context of online examination within distance education settings.

Statement of Problem

Previous research has focused on various aspects of online education, including instructor and student perspectives on online education applications (Tanyıldızı & Semerci, 2005; Torkul, Kibar & Tasci, 2004; Tufekci, Ekinçi & Kose, 2013), factors influencing online education (Aragon & Johnson, 2008), student learning strategies in online courses (Arend, 2007), challenges in online education (Çelen, Çelik & Seferoglu, 2011), technology in online education (Hillier & Fluck, 2017), and motivation in online education (Kawachi, 2003). These studies commonly highlight issues such as instructor time constraints, ethical concerns in online education, lack of information about online education, and deficiencies in technology literacy. However, the potential of online examination to enhance educational development in the Nigerian University context, particularly in distance education and blended learning, remains underexplored and warrants further investigation.

Research has delved into the comparability of online examinations with traditional face-to-face assessments, revealing that online examinations can offer similar levels of security and validity (Weiner & Hurtz, 2017; Smith., Clarke, Carmona & Cerimagic, 2017). Nevertheless, concerns persist regarding technical challenges such as internet connectivity and power availability, particularly in developing nations, which may compromise the validity of examination results (Ryznar, 2020). Additionally, issues related to privacy and human rights infringement have been raised (Tello, 2007; Williamson, 2018). Addressing these concerns within the context of distance education in Nigerian tertiary institutions constitutes a gap in the current study

Research Hypotheses

Ho1: Identified determinant variables has no positive influence on online examination adoption in open and distance education in Nigerian sampled University

Ho2: There is no relationship between Acceptability of Online Examination Practice and Educational Development in open and distance education in Nigerian sampled University

Literature Review

Concept of Online Examination Practice

Online examination describes the assessment of students learning with methods including information and communication technologies (Conrad & Openo, 2018). This does not restrict Online examination to fully online courses and can also be implemented in a blended learning format (Gikandi et al., 2011). Online assessments may take on different pedagogical functions as part of online learning environments (Webb & Ifenthaler, 2018), for example, scaffolding students to complete a task and measuring how much support they need or providing students with semantic rich and personalized feedback, as well as adaptive prompts for reflection (Gikandi et al., 2011). Other examples of online assessments include a pedagogical agent acting like a virtual coach tutoring learners and providing feedback when needed (Çelen, Çelik & Seferoglu, 2011) as well as an analysis of a learner's decisions during a digital game or simulation. Other online assessments use multimedia-constructed response items for authentic learning experiences or provide students with an emotionally engaging virtual world experience that unobtrusively documents the progression of a person's leadership and ethical development over time (Tufekci et al, 2013). Thus, online assessments offer a broad range of pedagogical functions including a medium for communication, a learning assistant, a judge, a test administrator, a performance prompt, a practice arena, or a performance workspace (Tufekci et al, 2013). Online assessment can be performed formatively throughout the learning progress or in a summative way at the end of a learning segment (Gikandi et al., 2011).

Post covid, research has found that faculty and academic administrators are becoming hesitant to continue adopting RPE due to concerns about the validity and security of the assessment process (Akaaboune et al., 2021; Paredes et al., 2021). While adopting these technologies is necessary during the covid-19 pandemic period, researchers believe it is vital to pause and think about the broader effects of implementing such technological "solutions" and examine how technology and assessment processes intersect with the broader objectives of education (Fawns & Schaepekens, 2022). Students, on the other hand, have mixed opinions, with some commending the flexibility, convenience, and positive exam experience availed by online examination (Anderson & Gades, 2017; Paredes et al., 2021), while others felt that OE is invasive and uncomfortable (Alessio et al., 2017; Kharbat & Abu-Daabes, 2021; Vasiliki et al., 2021). The effects of Online examination on student outcomes, including performance, motivation, and engagement, have also been studied. Some of these studies have found that online examination has a favourable effect on student motivation and engagement (Alessio et al., 2017; Cherry et al., 2021; Hall et al., 2021; Boldyrevskii et al., 2022), Others, however, have found no discernible difference between a remote and a conventional proctored exam (Vasiliki et al., 2021).

In the absence of coercion, the adoption of complex, new technologies such as OE is always slow, uncertain, and sometimes risky (Cho & McCardle, 2009). Most of the time, these

technologies are implemented with an expectation that is weighed against the cost, which might not necessarily be monetary (Heidenreich & Talke, 2021). The degree of ignorance, reluctance to change, worry about making the wrong decision, technological inadequacy, and other strange factors can also have an odd impact on how people accept new technologies.

Types, Modes, and Formats of Online Assessments/Examination

In the course of drawing inferences about students' learning process, online assessment can include different types of assessments, ranging from single- and multiple-choice quizzes, written exams or essays, and oral presentations to authentic assessments including project-based cases, games and simulations, or e-Portfolios (Conrad & Openo, 2018). (Audience Response Systems are not included in our definition of online assessment) The assessment process can be performed by different individuals or groups, i.e., different modes of assessment. Peers have the potential to take on the role of the assessor and provide each other with feedback. Learners might also self-assess by evaluating their learning process and outcome themselves or by reflecting on their learning (Conrad & Openo, 2018). Furthermore, the possibilities in online assessment also allow for automated assessment providing automated feedback (Gamage et al., 2020). In this systematic review, an online assessment format can either be formative or summative. An online assessment mode may be self-assessment, peer-assessment, teacher-assessment, or automated-assessment (system-based). An assessment type refers to the implemented task of the assessment. This might include for example quizzes, essays, e-Portfolios, project-based tasks, or others.

Empirical Study

Several studies have been conducted on stakeholder perceptions and attitudes towards the blended learning practice toward quality education in the context of distance education. Yinus *et al.* (2023) study Learner's Perception and Attitude toward Blended Learning Practice. questionnaire were administered to learners. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while the formulated hypotheses were tested through the use of Chi-Square at a 95% confidence level. The results of the study showed positive student perceptions toward blended learning practice. It is concluded that learners have a positive attitude towards the practice and quality of blended learning, but the problem of Internet access and the learner's lack of commitment outside the university campus form a major hindrance.

According to the study conducted by Okocha, Eyiolorunshe, and Oguntayo (2017) on student acceptance of blended learning in Nigeria, The research was carried out at the Centre for Learning Resources at Landmark University Omu-aran, Kwara State. The study explains the factors that influence the acceptance of blended learning and the level of acceptance of the features of blended learning by undergraduate students at Landmark University. Questionnaires were used as the instrument for data collection. The study found that performance expectations and facilitating conditions significantly influenced the acceptance of blended learning. In understanding the acceptance of blended learning features, the student shows more interest in course-related readings and course materials available on the learning management system and less interest in discussion with lecturers and discussion with classmates. It was also discovered that there is no relationship between the learning styles of students and their intention to adopt blended learning.

In Nangawe's study (2015), the adoption of ICT tools in Tanzanian Higher Learning Institutions (HLIs) was found to be closely linked to the attitudes of academic and non-

academic staff, with web-based assessment being moderately utilized to support student learning. However, despite its numerous advantages, online assessment remains underutilized in HLIs due to various challenges such as security concerns, lack of institutional e-assessment policies, and insufficient preparation and experience among instructors to effectively manage e-assessment systems (Appiah & Tonder, 2018). While integrating ICT into teaching is widely regarded as beneficial, progress in this area has been slow. Furthermore, the impact of online assessment on student learning in Tanzanian HLIs has not been extensively researched. Even when instructors attempt to leverage online assessment, they often encounter obstacles that impede implementation. Thus, there is a pressing need to identify and address the barriers to online examination within the context of distance education in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Suleiman, Salaudeen, and Falode (2017) explored the effects of a computer-based blended learning strategy on chemistry students' retention in individualized and collaborative settings in Minna, Nigeria. Using a quasi-experimental design, they compared outcomes among three groups: individualized, collaborative, and lecture methods, finding collaborative settings yielded better retention. Similarly, Marchalot et al. (2017) evaluated blended learning's impact on medical residents' performance in France, showing improved scores post-intervention compared to traditional teaching. Shorey et al. (2017) studied blended learning's influence on nursing students' communication skills in Singapore, reporting positive effects on satisfaction, attitudes, and self-efficacy.

Gaps in the Literature

These studies collectively highlight the effectiveness of distance and eLearning across diverse disciplines and educational contexts. This study contributes to the existing literature by exploring stakeholder perceptions of distance education while emphasizing the critical role of learning feedback in ensuring quality education within the context of open and distance learning in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Specifically, it evaluates the acceptance and adoption of online examination practices and their influence on educational development, addressing a significant gap in the literature. By integrating the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) as a theoretical framework, the study provides deeper insights into the factors influencing the acceptance and use of online examinations. Key constructs such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions are explored to understand their impact on the adoption of online examination practices. Furthermore, the study contributes to the education and digital economy by focusing on the integration of technology to enhance educational development and accessibility, filling a notable gap in research on technology-driven educational practices in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Methodology

An online survey design was employed, the population of the study comprises of all 216 staff members of LODLC ranging from Learner Support Services (LSS), Information and Guidance (IAG), Technical Support (TS), etutor/Lecturers for both online and face-to-face lecture facilitation and the centre administrators purposively. This is based on their active involvement in an online examination exercise. The selection of Ladoke Akintola University (LAUTECH) is based on the fact that they are stakeholders in educational sector especially in distance education. Also based on their forefront participation in an online examination practice among

Nigerian university that embrace open and distance education. A total of 197 questionnaires were completed and returned, yielding a 91% retrieval rate. The collected data were analysis with aid of descriptive analysis like table and percentage while inferential statistics such as correlation, multiple regression analysis and ANOVA were employed to analyse the formulated hypothesis. All analysis were done at 95% confidence level.

Results and Discussion

Analysis of Economic Demographic data of the Respondents

As presented in Table 1 the total number of participants in this study was 197, 59.4% of the participants were male and 40.6% were female. The largest age group was found to be in the 20 to 30 range, representing 34% of the respondent. Almost all participants (96.4%) had prior experience with OEP. LSS/Etutor/Lecturers formed the largest group based on their academic rank (38.1%), followed by IA&G officers (24%) and the administrators (14%) while professors, facilitators, technical support and help desk officers account for the remaining 22%. These findings indicated that the majority of the stakeholders in the selected higher institutions were represented.

Table 1: Demography

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	117	59.39
	Female	80	40.61
Age	20 – 30	67	34.01
	31 – 40	65	32.99
	40 – 50	55	27.92
	Above 51	10	5.08
	Have you done or involve in an OEP?	Yes	190
	No	7	3.55
Rank	Professors	10	5.08
	LSS/Etutor/Lecturers	75	38.07
	Facilitators	22	11.17
	Technical Support	9	4.57
	Administrators	29	14.72
	IA&G officer	48	24.37
	Help Desk officer	4	2.03

OEP: Online Examination Practice

Source: Author's Computation, (2024).

Table 2: Responses on Stakeholders Perception on Variable of Online Examination Adoption Components

Variable	Response
Effort expectancy	Effort expectancy positively affects the behavioural intention to use Online Examination
Social Influence	Social Influence positively affects the behavioural intention to use Online Examination
Performance expectancy	Performance expectancy positively affects the behavioural intention to use Online Examination
Price Value	Price Value positively affects the behavioural intention to use Online Examination
Personal innovation	Personal innovation positively affects the behavioural intention to use Online Examination
Facilitating condition	Facilitating condition positively affects the behavioural intention to use Online Examination

Reliability test of the study variables

Table 3: Reliability Test

Factors	Cronbach's Alpha
Performance Expectancy	0.929
Effort Expectancy	0.925
Social Influence	0.831
Facilitating Condition	0.148
Price Value	0.741
Personal Innovation	0.679

Source: Author's Computation, (2024).

The findings of the reliability study as presented in tables show that the variables under consideration exhibit various degrees of internal consistency. Performance Expectancy (0.929), Effort Expectancy (0.925), Social Influence (0.831), Price Value (0.741) are high reliability variables with values that are near to 1. Although Personal Innovation (0.679) has a value below the generally agreed lower limit of 0.70 for Cronbach's alpha, it is still considered acceptable based on agitation of Hair et al., (2006), who stated that it can decrease to 0.60 and still be acceptable. Therefore, Personal innovativeness is acceptable in this study. Cronbach's alpha value for the Facilitating Conditions factor is 0.148, which is well below the generally accepted lower limit of 0.70. Consequently, it will not be considered in our analysis.

Correlation Analysis

Table 4: Correlation matrix

	PE	EE	SI	PV	PI
PE	1				
EE	.838**	1			
SI	.772**	.701**	1		
PV	.761**	.746**	.761**	1	

PI	.497**	.506**	.587**	.546**	1
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** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author’s Computation, (2024).

Based on the values in the correlation matrix presented Table 4, The correlation coefficients range from .497 to .838, such that the highest correlation coefficient is between PE and EE, SI and PV (.838, 0.772 and 0.801). This indicates that there is correlations between the dependent and independent variables and they all had positive linear associations that were significant at 0.01 ($p < 0.01$).

Multiple regressions analysis

Analysis in Table 5 showed the regression model summary, it was observed that the R Square (R^2) value is 0.692, which means that 69.2% change in online examination behavioural intention toward acceptance and adoption due to changes in the PE, EE, PV, PI and SI. The result of multiple regression model presented in table 5b further in indicate a unit increase in all the identify variables such as PE, EE, PV, PI and SI increase adoption of online examination practice by 0.4, 0.1, 0.1, 0.8, 0.1, and 0.1 respectively, this indicate that all the independent variables incorporated into the model were significantly related to online examination practice.

Table 5a: Regression model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.832a	0.692	0.680	0.77629

a. Predictors: (Constant), Personal Innovativeness, Performance Expectancy, Social Influence, Price Value, Effort Expectancy

Source: Author’s Computation, (2024).

Table 5b: Regression model

Mode		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	0.355	0.166		2.141	0.034
	Performance Expectancy	0.113	0.038	0.270	3.015	0.003
	Effort Expectancy	0.003	0.034	0.008	0.100	0.921
	Social Influence	0.083	0.035	0.177	2.355	0.020
	Price Value	0.124	0.067	0.142	1.844	0.067
	Personal Innovativeness	0.137	0.047	0.161	2.944	0.004

Source: Author’s Computation, (2024).

Stakeholder Perception on relationship between Online Examination Practice and Educational Development.

The descriptive analysis results presented in Table 6 shows stakeholders perception on relationship between Online Examination Practice and Educational Development in the selected university. The result shows that (71%) of the stakeholders of the selected university in ODL unit were opined that Acceptability of online education practice easy education development. Also, (99%) of the respondent is also of the opinion that distance learning Practice align with the standard of education system. (81.22%) of the stakeholders opined that Academic performance will be better with effective online education practice than the traditional system of Education. These results highlight a strong consensus among stakeholders regarding the positive impact of online education practices on educational development and performance. The high level of agreement suggests that stakeholders recognize the potential of online examination systems to enhance learning outcomes, align with global educational standards, and provide a viable alternative to traditional methods. This underscores the need for universities to invest in and prioritize the development of robust online education infrastructures and policies. Such investments could improve academic performance, foster broader acceptance of online education, and contribute to achieving educational goals in line with international best practices

Table 6: Analysis of relationship between Online Examination Practice and Educational Development

Variable	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Undecided
Acceptability of online education practice easy education development	105(53.3)	35(17.77)	-	-	57(28.93)
Distance Learning Practice align with the standard of education system	166(84.27)	30(15.23)	-	1(0.51)	-
Academic performance will be better with effective online education practice than the traditional system of Education	92(46.7)	68(34.52)	20(10.15)	17(8.63)	-

Source: Author’s Computation, (2024).

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1, which states that identified determinant variables have no positive influence on online examination adoption in open and distance education in Nigerian sampled universities, was tested using multiple regression analysis. The results, as shown in Table 5, indicate an R^2 value of 69.2%. This implies that 69.2% of the variation in online examination behavioral intention toward acceptance and adoption can be attributed to changes in the identified determinant variables, namely Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE), Perceived Value (PV), Perceived Interactivity (PI), and Social Influence (SI). Additionally, the analysis demonstrates that a unit increase in each of these variables results in a corresponding increase in the adoption of online examination practices. This finding underscores the significance of these independent variables in influencing online examination adoption. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that the identified determinant variables have a positive influence on online examination adoption in open and distance education. **The hypothesis 2**, which posits that there is no relationship between the acceptability of online examination practices and educational development, was tested using ANOVA. The results reveal an F-statistic value of 30.078, with a significance level ($p < .001$), as presented in Table 7. The high F-value indicates that the variability between group means is significantly larger than the variability within groups, providing strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table 7: Test of Hypotheses 2 Using ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	97.357	4	24.3393	30.078	.000
Within Groups	98.826	192	.7065		
Total	196.183	196			

Source: Author's Computation, (2024).

Discussion of Findings

The findings reveal that Performance Expectancy (PE), Social Influence (SI), and Personal Innovativeness (PI) significantly influence the adoption of online examination practices in Nigerian universities. Among these factors, Performance Expectancy emerged as the most significant predictor of stakeholders' behavioral intentions toward online examinations. This underscores the perception among stakeholders that online examinations provide an effective, secure, and reliable means of assessing knowledge and skills, contributing to a streamlined and efficient examination process. Furthermore, the study confirms that all the identified determinant variables positively influence the adoption of online examinations in open and distance education settings. These findings align with previous research (Alwahaishi & Snasel, 2013; Shorey et al., 2017), which highlights the importance of these factors in driving the acceptance and implementation of online assessments. The results also demonstrate a significant relationship between the acceptability of online examination practices and

educational development. This implies that adopting online examination practices is positively associated with enhanced educational outcomes, reinforcing the need for uniformity in policies, standards, and practices to ensure effective implementation. The findings align with the perspectives of Yinus et al. (2023) and Suleiman, Salaudeen, and Falode (2017), who emphasized that distance and eLearning practices incorporating online assessments and feedback significantly enhance learners' performance and align with educational standards, outperforming traditional teaching methods.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the findings, the study concludes that Performance Expectancy, Social Influence, and Personal Innovativeness are critical determinants of online examination adoption and are positively associated with educational development. These factors play a vital role in fostering the acceptance and successful implementation of online examination practices, ultimately enhancing educational outcomes. Accordingly, it is recommended that Nigerian universities, particularly those embracing distance education, prioritize improving technology infrastructure and investing in capacity building to strengthen online examination systems and practices.

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